

Dynamic Eclipse Broadcast (DEB) Initiative Software Installation for Windows 10/11 1 July 2025 (DEB Information at debinitiative.org)

Follow these procedures to install the 3rd party software for the DEB project. You can skip any step that you have already completed.

You may need to have some of these websites whitelisted by your institution to download and install some programs.

Several of these installs may cause the Windows Protect to come up. Select **More Info** (Right image) and you can then select to run the installation.

STEP 1 – PYTHON INSTALLATION

Install python with python installer if you **don't** have a python package

CHECK FOR EXISTING PYTHON!

Open Command Prompt by typing 'cmd' in Windows search bar and selecting 'Command Prompt'

Type 'python --version' in command prompt

If python version is between 3.8... and 3.11... skip to STEP 2
Otherwise, continue below with STEP 1

We recommend Miniconda for this

[Miniconda — miniconda documentation](https://docs.miniconda.org/)

Open Miniconda3 installer provided in DEB software folder

Do not use a miniconda version above py311...

Select Next

Select I agree to License Agreement

Select your preference here, but the default, 'Just Me,' is our recommendation as well as Anaconda's

Select Next

Note: instructions do not cover other options here, so be sure you know what are you doing if you vary from these instructions

Use the default destination folder

WRITE THIS ADDRESS DOWN. YOU WILL NEED IT!!!

Select Next

Note: instructions do not cover other options here, so be sure you know what are you doing if you vary from these instructions

- Select the options here
- Create start menu shortcuts
 - Register Miniconda3 as my default Python 3.11
 - Clear the package cache upon completion

Click install and finish when complete.

STEP 2 – SHARPCAP INSTALL

Install SharpCap 4.1 (64 bit)	Downloads – SharpCap – Lunar, Planetary, Solar and Deep Sky Imaging. EAA and Live Stacking.
Agree and install	
Click Launch	

The program will open with an initial information panel that you must close (image of information panel not included)

Add Pro License

Select 'Help' and 'SharpCap Pro License'

The License Key window will then open

You will need to request the license.txt file from your DEB contact


```
File Edit Format View Help
LicenseId = #####
Expiry = #####
Feature = SharpCapPro
FeatureId = #####
LicensedTo = #####
Signature0 = #####
Signature1 = #####
Signature2 = #####
```

Copy the data in the license.txt file by clicking “control” + “a” and then “control” + “c” in the text file while it is open in the Notepad text editor


```
File Edit Format View Help
LicenseId = #####
Expiry = #####
Feature = SharpCapPro
FeatureId = #####
LicensedTo = #####
Signature0 = #####
Signature1 = #####
Signature2 = #####
```

Go back to SharpCap and use “control” + “v” to paste the license information into the box

Click ok and then you should get a message that the license is valid

You can close SharpCap now

SharpCap Pro License

You need a License Key to enable SharpCap Pro Features.

[Learn more about SharpCap Pro](#) Purchase SharpCap Pro License...

```
LicenseId = #####
Expiry = #####
Feature = SharpCapPro
FeatureId = #####
LicensedTo = #####
Signature0 = #####
Signature1 = #####
Signature2 = #####
```

License Is: Valid

Expiry Date:

Licensed To:

Restrictions: None

OK Cancel

STEP 3 – ASCOM PlayerOne Camera Setup

You must have the **ASCOM platform** installed first

Open the provided installer or follow the link and click on the Download button in the window most similar to the one shown here

[Download Center \(ascom-standards.org\)](https://www.ascom-standards.org)

Follow the instructions and use the default settings to install

Install ASCOM PlayerOne Camera Driver

Open the provided installer or follow the link and select the “Camera ASCOM Driver...” version shown here

[Software – Player One Astronomy \(player-one-astronomy.com\)](https://www.player-one-astronomy.com)

ASCOM Driver			
ASCOM platform	The ASCOM platform is an astronomical standard protocol set running on the windows system. Many astronomy software need to be installed after the ASCOM platform can be used. You can log on to the ASCOM platform official website for more information.	V6.5	Released: 2020/5/20 Official Download ASCOM6.5 Download
Camera ASCOM Driver (base on ASCOM6.5)	Software using ASCOM interface, need to be installed to control the camera. ASCOM6.5 platform is required.	V6.5.8.1	Released: 2025/03/28 Download

Select Setup Language

Accept the agreement

Install the program
Click "Finish" when done installing

STEP 4 – Player one camera driver install

Use the provided installer or follow the link and select Native Driver>Camera Driver

[Software – Player One Astronomy \(player-one-astronomy.com\)](https://player-one-astronomy.com)

Native Driver				
Camera Driver	Only Windows users must install the native driver to use the camera. (Windows7SP1 or later) Looking for the driver on Windows on ARM? Please check this: Camera native driver on Windows11 on arm (Windows11 in Parallels on Apple silicon Mac)	V1.5.3.21	Released: 2025/03/28	Download

You should see an install window similar to this

Select install

You may be prompted to continue with install multiple times by Windows

Click "Finish" when installation complete

STEP 5 – iOptronCommander ASCOM Driver

<p>Open the provided installer or follow the link and select “Latest Version > Commander and ASCOM Driver Installer X.X.X.X”</p>	<p>ioptron.com/Articles.asp?ID=337</p> <p>Latest Version Commander and ASCOM Driver Installer 9.2.0.1 (Released 4/2/2025)</p>
<p>Accept the License Agreement</p>	<p>License Agreement</p> <p>Please read the following important information before continuing.</p> <p>Please read the following License Agreement. You must accept the terms of this agreement before continuing with the installation.</p> <p>This work is licensed under the Creative Commons Attribution-No Derivative Works 3.0 License. To view a copy of this license, visit http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-nd/3.0/ or send a letter to Creative Commons, 171 Second Street, Suite 300, San Francisco, California, 94105, USA.</p> <p><input checked="" type="radio"/> I accept the agreement <input type="radio"/> I do not accept the agreement</p> <p>Next Cancel</p>
<p>Select install and it will run</p>	<p>Ready to Install</p> <p>Setup is now ready to begin installing iOptron Commander and ASCOM Driver on your computer.</p> <p>Click Install to continue with the installation.</p> <p>Back Install Cancel</p> <p>Completing the iOptron Commander and ASCOM Driver Setup Wizard</p> <p>Setup has finished installing iOptron Commander and ASCOM Driver on your computer. The application may be launched by selecting the installed shortcuts.</p> <p>Click Here to exit Setup.</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> View iOptron Update History</p> <p>Finish</p>

STEP 6 – FITS Liberator 3.0 (this is FITS file viewing program from ESO/ESA/NASA)

<p>Select the FL_30_Win installer or follow link to download</p>	<p>Download the ESA/ESO/NASA FITS Liberator v3.0 ESA/Hubble ESA/Hubble (esahubble.org)</p>
<p>Download and run the setup file</p>	<p>FITS Liberator 3.0 Setup</p> <p>Welcome to the FITS Liberator 3.0 Setup Wizard</p> <p>This wizard will guide you through the installation of FITS Liberator 3.0. Please check the following before continuing:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - If FITS Liberator is running, you must close it before starting Setup. <p>Click Next to continue.</p> <p>Next > Cancel</p>

Accept the license agreement terms

Select next

Make sure both boxes are checked. Click install

STEP 7 – Install Planetary System Stacker with Python

<p>Open vs_BuildTools or follow link and select the "Community" > Free download</p> <p>Run installer</p>	<p>Download Visual Studio Tools - Install Free for Windows, Mac, Linux (microsoft.com)</p>
<p>Install C++ build tools with vs_BuildTools (you might not see this window)</p>	
<p>The installer may take some time to install</p>	
<p>Scroll down to the Desktop and Mobile section</p> <p>Select the "Desktop development with C++" as seen here</p> <p>You need the 5 blue checked boxes (far right of image)</p> <p>Click install (Bottom Right)</p>	

Open a command prompt just like you did in Step 1

If you have installed python with these instructions, you will now use the address for miniconda3 you saved in Step 1

With Miniconda it should be something like:
C:\Users\yourcomputerloginname\miniconda3\python
In the next commands this address will be referred to as: *pathToPython\python*

With other installations the above address might be unnecessary, and you can just use "python" instead of "pathToPython\python"

If neither of these works, email your DEB contact for further information.

Install Planetary System Stacker with python

This will take a few minutes

Type: *pathToPython\python -m pip install planetary_system_stacker*

Upgrade numpy to compatible version (Best to use the exact command to the right)

You cannot use numpy 2.xx.x

Type: *pathToPython\python -m pip install --force-reinstall numpy==1.26.0*

Go to Windows File Explorer

and locate `planetary_system_stacker.py`

See below for instructions of finding this location

If you installed Python with miniconda the installation will be in this location →
SKIP TO NEXT GREEN PANEL

C:\Users\username\miniconda3\Lib\site-packages\planetary_system_stacker

If **not a miniconda installation**, these instructions should help you locate the installation

Open a file explorer window

Enter '`C:\Users\yourcomputerloginname\AppData`' in address bar, hit return

Enter '`planetary_system_stacker.py`' in the search bar

When it appears in the window, **right click** on the file and select "Open File Location"

You should see a screen similar to this

Replace pss_console.py in this folder:

- 1) Change the name of the existing pss_console.py to pss_console_backup.py
- 2) Copy or move the pss_console.py you downloaded from DEB into this location

RESTART COMPUTER

Congratulations!!

You have successfully installed all of the required 3rd party software.

NEXT: Open the 'DEB_scripts' folder you downloaded from DEB and follow the instructions in 'Python-Script-Installation-and-Setup' to continue the setup.

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